

Master's Thesis On

***Consumer Perception Towards Fintech company
Comparison Between Paytm and Phone pe***

***FOR THE PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENT
FOR THE AWARD OF
MASTER OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION***

**UNDER THE GUIDANCE OF
Dr. /Prof. Fatima Qasim Hasan**

**Submitted By
(UDESHYA MOHAN)
20GSOB2010050**

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**School of Business
Galgotias University**

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Galgotias University

May, 2022

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This is to certify that the Master's Thesis "consumer perception Towards Fintech company comparison Between Phone pe and Paytm" has been prepared by Mr. Udeshya Mohan under my supervision and guidance. The project report is submitted towards the partial fulfillment of 2 year, Full time Master of Business Administration.

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I, **Udeshya Mohan** Roll No.(20GSOB2010050) student of School of Business, Galgotias University, Greater Noida, hereby declare that the Master's Thesis on "consumer perception Towards Fintech company comparison Between Phone pe and Paytm" is an original and authenticated work done by me.

I further declare that it has not been submitted elsewhere by any other person in any of the institutes for the award of any degree or diploma.

Udeshya Mohan

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Abstract

The thesis is attempt to make a comparative analysis of the services provided by Paytm and Phone pe. The study also is an attempt to understand the market share of these companies the study was undertaken in the Delhi Ncr region The study shows that the services pr0ovided by Paytm is far superior than Phone pe in terms of User interface, Application speed and Cashback discounts offered to the users. The Transaction value of Paytm was higher than Phone pe in the year 2021.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to give warmest gratefulness to my faculty mentor and supervisor **Dr./Prof. Fatima Qasim Hasan** for bringing the weight of his considerable experience and knowledge to this research work named “**consumer perception Towards Fintech company: A comparison Between Phone pe and Paytm**”. Her continuous guidance and fetching out the most relevant and practical topic for the research so that I can grind my own knowledge. I perceive as this opportunity as a big milestone in my career development. I will strive to use gained skills and knowledge in the best possible way, and I will continue to work on their improvement, in order to attain desired career objectives. Hope to continue cooperation with good people in future. As we have come to our end journey of being a professional course, this project will add on more value to my professional life coming ahead. This research work will emphasis towards the current scenario of the market and polish my understanding of various issues and problems faced by general public. I will make sure to gain that learning in this project that will enhance my knowledge and area of specialization.

TABLE OF CONTENT

TABLE OF CONTENTS		
1	Introduction	
2	Review of literature	
3	Research Methodology	
4	Data analysis and interpretation	
5	Conclusion	
6	References	

Introduction

The term “fintech company” refers to any business that uses technology to transform, develop, or automate the financial services of businesses or consumers. Financial technology (abbreviated fintech or FinTech) is a new technology and innovation aimed at competing with traditional financial systems in the delivery of financial services. It is an emerging industry that uses technology to improve jobs in finance. The use of smartphones in mobile banking, investment, borrowing services, and cryptocurrency are technical examples aimed at making financial services more accessible to the general public. Financial technology companies include both established financial institutions and technology companies trying to replace or improve the use of financial services provided by existing financial companies. A subset of fintech companies focused on the insurance industry are collectively Paytm is a form of Indian electronic payment and e-commerce product based in Delhi NCR, India. Launched in August 2010, it is a subsidiary of the parent company One97 Communications. The name is an acronym for "Payment through Mobile." The company has employed more than 13,000 employees since January 2017 and has 3 million offline vendors across India. It also uses Paytm payment gateway and Paytm Wallet.

Among other sources of funding, in 2015, Paytm became the first Indian company to receive funding from China E-Commerce Company Alibaba, after raising more than \$ 625 million worth \$ 1.5 billion. Alibaba Group played a key role in Paytm's parent company One97 Communications

Paytm was founded and launched by One97 Communications Limited in 2010 as a mobile recharge website. In an interview, its founder Vijay Shekhar Sharma recounted how he was inspired when he visited China, when he saw vegetable sellers using cell phones to get payments from other customers. This led to the launch of the Paytm wallet in 2013.

In 2013, the company launched Paytm Wallet, which became India's largest mobile payment service platform with over 150 million wallets and 75 million downloads of Android-based apps since November 2016. The increase in service usage has been largely due to performance of money of 500. and 1000 rupee notes. After the 8th of November 2016, Paytm transactions and profits went up significantly.

In 2015 Paytm obtained a license from the Reserve Bank of India to start one of India's first payment banks, called "Paytm Payments Bank Limited" At the time, the bank intended to use existing Paytm users to offer new services, including cards. debit, saving. accounts, online

banking and money transfer, so that the economy does not have money. The pay bank will be a separate business where founder Vijay Shekhar Sharma will hold 51%, One97 Communications will hold 39% and 10% will be owned by One97 and Sharma.

Paytm Payments Bank became operational on May 23, 2017, initially with an invitation-only program. As of August 31, 2017, banking services have been open to the public through the Paytm Android and iOS app.

In May 2017 Paytm Launched Paytm Payment Bank For Paytm Users In Wallet. And in May 2017, Paytm was reportedly in talks to pump \$ 30 million into Insider to get a bigger share. In July 2017, Paytm acquired a large Insider in, allowing its users to book events instantly.

In June 2017, Paytm Mall, a newly launched online market place organization based in Noida, confirmed that it was cataloging more than 1,000 car and two wheeler vehicles to increase internet usage and offline sales. In June 2017, the Economic Times reported that Paytm was seeking a license to establish a wallet market so that its users could keep cash and earn interest on it. They were awaiting approval as they had applied to the Central Bank of India for the establishment of the fund

PhonePe or PhonePe Private Limited is an Indian e-commerce payment service and digital wallet company. PhonePe was launched in 2015 by its founders, Mr. Sameer Nigam and Rahul Chari were also the first payment app in India built on integrated payments.

Visual connector i.e. (UPI). PhonePe is now available in 11 languages. Phone Pe offers a variety of services.

The Phone Pe app has over 100 million users and has crossed over 5 billion transactions.

The latest development of the Phone Pe app is that it allows its customers to withdraw cash using its UPI feature in the app also known as the Phone Pe ATM, which means to transfer a specified amount to be issued to your nearest Phone Pe enabled vendor / retailer.

The rapid growth of mobile technology around the world is a very significant trend largely because of the prepaid model. As a result, all sections of the community are now able to access financial services as people become more familiar with the financial system.

In fact, mobile technology, regarded as a payment or banking channel, has the potential to allow two key questions to be resolved simultaneously: on the demand side, it represents the opportunity to invest among the population under common rules. banking services. In terms of

service delivery, it opens up opportunities for financial institutions to deliver a wide range of services at low cost to many clients in the poorest sections of society and to people living in remote areas.

Although there are more than 120 mobile projects made in about 70 emerging markets (Beshouri et al. 2010), mobile payment has become commonplace in a few countries, despite your great potential. The lack of universal distribution of such a powerful service indicates that successful cases are not well understood, and as a result, not easily repeated. This suggests that lessons are not learned in areas where the program has been successfully adopted. In addition, we suspect that barriers to its adoption in many countries are not investigated sufficiently investigated to allow implementation strategies to be implemented on the basis of reliable business models.

Benefits of using Paytm Payment Gateway

- It is easy to accept payment with multiple payment sources.
- Higher security of payments.
- High levels of success in the industry.
- Easy withdrawal with saved cards.
- T + 1 bank accommodation.
- Business growth details in Paytm Merchant Dashboard

Benefits a of Phonepe

- . Fast and easy recharge.
- . A problem-free payment to the Seller.
- . Easy Bill Payment Kanye Autopay.
- . UPI Fund Transfer.
- . One app for many services.
- . Slightly Secure (Does not require a PIN or password to unlock)
- . Delay in payment.
- . Non-Credit of Money.

Any delay in payment Services

Pay tm have the option of recharging and shopping from whenever, anywhere and access from wherever they are. Before opting, pay tm people should think twice or not whether they provide service. Pay tm plays a significant role in payment of online transactions, but they suffer from the technological barriers as server may busy. According to the survey, it shows greater volume for positive i.e. 60% people have agreed that there is no delay in payment and 40% people have disagreed between 18 to 30 years. Even there is a positive reaction in 30 to 45 years, as 80% people agreed and 20% people disagreed. The disagreed people have told about that they have recharge mobile for Rs.100 but for 40-45 min it did not process and did not refund to bank a/c. this error was due to technical fault in pay tm. Pay tm have the option of recharging and shopping

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Security system

Nowadays, pay tm offers advanced account protection to gain this we have to login to additional layer of security on pay tm website. Pay tm has designed 2 step authentications to keep safe and secure our pay tm in mobile applications.

This feature is to make sure our account safe always. As the security system is available to all in advanced way, people are well known about the attractive security training; majority of people i.e. 100% have satisfied with this between 30-40 years. Meanwhile, between 18-30 years' age group 16 people are agreed and 4 people are disagreed because all of them are vulnerable to password thefts. To secure our pay tm transactions, we tend to use same password on all platforms and websites for our convenience

Problems encountered while making payments

Pay tm strongly believes in a sincere and transparent approach to its users. Pay tm treats the users fairly all times and encounter the problems and they take care of all complaints effectively. As the main aim of pay tm is at minimising customer complaints, grievances and reviews and redressal as they give first preference to customers to solve their problems

Objective of the thesis

- Comparison in terms of services provided phone pay and paytm
- To study the transaction value of both the companies.

Need of Study

There are many fintech companies in India which offer payment gateway to the consumers.

In this research we will try to find out what the users of these platforms are expecting from their respective usage of the following platforms. The basic difference on the customer perspective could lead us to the knowledge how the online platforms are different from others and why they are preferred by their users.

Review of Literature

In this study, the discussion about this report contains the basic introduction about both of the organizations, also it includes the difference between the companies on the basis of various aspects, Paytm and phone pe.

Myersin (1969) stated that the vast majority of the innovation are essentially advertise driven and is acquainted as an answer with the particular needs of the customer.

Lynn (1966) states that more development is presented in Consumer Market when contrasted with mechanical markets. Galbraith (1970).

Prof Trilok Nath Shukla in his paper “Mobile Wallet: Present and the Future” (June 2016) has discussed about mobile wallet, working, types and its advantages and disadvantages. His analysis included perception of consumers and retailers about mobile wallets. He concluded that mobile wallets will be used to engage with the customer by the marketers and digital businesses. Irrespective of the market status of these mobile wallets, marketers should take advantage of the emerging opportunities.

Key Pousttchi and Dietmar G. Wiedemann in their paper “What Influences Consumers’ Intention to Use Mobile Payments?” (2008) studied the adoption of mobile payments and evaluated what key influences affected consumers to use mobile payments and found that subjective security was not a primary driver of mobile payment acceptance. They found that perceived confidentiality of payment details and perceived trustworthiness were strongly correlated. Four key variables were found to directly impacting consumer intention and usage behavior: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions.

Dr. Poonam Painuly, Shalu Rathi in their paper “Mobile Wallet: An upcoming mode of business transactions” (May 2016) clearly explains about the mobile wallet, it’s types and latest trends. At that point examined about Role of portable wallet in different divisions like Banks, Retail and Hospitality. The paper clarifies the significance of versatile wallet for Banks, Customers and Companies. In future extension it also discusses on the versatile wallets turning into a trend of advertising channel in not so distant future. Also, contributing exceedingly in a consistent shopping knowledge for the clients that expansion their inclination for regular and more repurchases with delightful encounters. They additionally talk on the significance and development of portable cash in business, social and monetary planned. The nearness of versatile wallet spreading from urban to country territories on a huge scale. Henceforth, wallet cash sees a high splendid future in close time.

FE Bureau (2017) states that According to the RBI: Demonetization has increased the growth of Paytm & Mobi Kwik which is known as the Digital payment companies. “A Newspaper Article in Financial Express”.

Research has shown that there is flexibility, which has a significant impact on customer behavior and its target for mobile purchasing, and most importantly **PEOU (Luna et al., 2019)**. While performing banking services on mobile phones, customers opt for a simple and easy-to-use user plan

Chawla (2019) collected data from 744 respondents and discovered that trust, easy to use and security have an effect on the attitude of consumers to use e-wallets.

Girija (2019) collected data from 150 respondents and revealed that cash back offers and convenience are the main reasons to use ewallets.

Senthil (2019) surveyed 150 respondents and found that users are satisfied with Paytm services as it resolves the problem within 24 hours.

Sivakumar and Balaji (2019) got responses from 100 respondents and discovered that there is no significant relationship between age and use of Paytm.

DS Soegoto & MP Tampubolon (2020) in their research work, E-wallet as a payment Instrument in the millennial era explained that E – wallet does have a role in the public transaction activities lately due to the effectiveness and efficiency of transaction and the security services provided to them.

Research Methodology

Area of Research-

The study was conducted in Delhi & NCR region

Type of Study-

The study was descriptive in nature. This descriptive study compares the services provided by phone pe and Paytm.

Sample Size-

This study was conducted in a systematic manner such as determining the sample method,

Sampling is a system for identifying and selecting samples from individuals for research.

The researcher submitted the google form along with it reached a separate group of 200 respondents who gave their opinion when completed list of questions.

170 respondents to receive data analysis using PayTm and Phone Pay or both mobile wallets.

It the researchers used the first and second data collected from respondents and other resources.

Basic data collected with the help of google queries sent to users,

Data Type-

Primary Data- Google form were shared with 200 respondents.

Secondary data was collected from various sources such as articles published in various journals and newspapers, published books, magazines, conference papers, worksheets, and websites, etc

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Objective 1

Comparative analysis between Phone pe and Paytm		
	Phone pe (Rs)	Paytm(Rs)
Payment Limit	1,00000	3,00000
Deduction of wallet from users bank A/c	No	Yes
Application speed	Slow	Fast
Cashback on recharge	No	Yes

User transaction limit

The transaction limit in Paytm is more as compared to Phone pe. Paytm provides a limit of 3 lakhs whereas Phone pe limit is 1 Lakh.

Toll

From PhonePe money is deducted directly from the users bank account at the time of payment. But it does not add to the phone pe wallet. On the other hand, in Paytm the money is directly transferred to the wallet. . This is one of the contributing factor for the popularity of Paytm over Phone pe..

Application speed

The first time users usually find it difficult to make a payment on Phonepe, on the other hand, it is much easier to use on Paytm . Coming to the app speed,, it is clear that Paytm is faster than PhonePe when it comes to global transaction speed.

Cashback on recharge

it difficult for users to pay. PhonePe and Paytm have explicit functionality, so they are already limited in Paytm. Not to mention, they also have an automated billing payment on the same day cash refund in paytm but phone pe does not provide cash refund on the same day.

To sum up, although Paytm and PhonePe hold their own position in the payment app market in India, Paytm excels in terms of total user usage, application speed, and payment location.

Objective 2

PhonePe Transaction Value In CY21

Paytm Transaction Value In CY21

Source: Paytm and Phone pe website

Paytm and Phone Pe

Paytm transactions costing INR 80,508 Cr, a 31% monthly increase from September inclusive of INR 61,417 Cr. The pay giant was almost 9% of the UPI market share in 2021 registering payments worth INR 6.7 Lakh Cr.

PhonePe has been leading the industry in all key metrics including number and number of jobs, registered users and vendor inclusion. The first to be a market leader in the UPI with a market share of over 46% in the volume of activities considered last year

CONCLUSION

This thesis has extensively analysed academic and non-academic papers related to the important topic of paytm and Phone pe . After searching significant sources to identify who (researchers and institutions) is publishing what (the related topics) and where (the countries studied, journals and databases), this paper has attempted to provide a comprehensive picture of the knowledge production and dissemination of mobile for payments around the world.

PayTm supports their customers to transfer their payments with the usage of their mobile phones in the easiest way. PayTm is a good app to download due to its wide network of partners which makes it convenient to use. Phone pe has to work upon the Payment gateway to improve the transaction efficiency. PayTm is currently performing well in terms of cashback whereas Phone pe has to work upon discounts/offers, transaction time and bring about innovation to increase customer satisfaction.

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The term "fintech company" refers to any business that uses technology to transform, develop, or automate the financial services of businesses or consumers. Financial technology (abbreviated fintech or FinTech) is a new technology and innovation aimed at competing with traditional financial systems in the delivery of financial services. It is an emerging industry that uses technology to improve jobs in finance. The use of smartphones in mobile banking, investment, borrowing services, and cryptocurrency are technical examples aimed at making financial services more accessible to the general public. Financial technology companies include both established financial institutions and technology companies trying to replace or improve the use of financial services provided by existing financial companies. A subset of fintech companies focused on the insurance industry are collectively Paytm is a form of Indian electronic payment and e-commerce product based in Delhi NCR, India. Launched in August 2010, it is a subsidiary of the parent company One97 Communications. The name is an acronym for "Payment through Mobile." The company has employed more than 13,000 employees since January 2017 and has 3 million offline vendors across India. It also uses Paytm payment gateway and Paytm Wallet.

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